

Nicotine Replacement therapy

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Abstract

In 1980, a pivotal moment occurred in the field of mental health with the inclusion of "nicotine dependence" in the third edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM). Tobacco dependence is defined as, "Cluster of behavioural, cognitive and physiological phenomena that develop after repeated tobacco use and that typically include a strong desire to use tobacco, difficulties in controlling its use, persistence in tobacco use despite harmful consequences, a higher priority given to tobacco use than other activities and obligations, increased tolerance and sometimes a physical withdrawal state."¹ Both smoked and smokeless forms of tobacco contain nicotine, a highly addictive chemical, making it difficult for habituated tobacco users to quit. Google Scholar was utilized to take an initial sample of what types of articles are available. We searched other databases like PubMed, EMBASE, COCHRANE LIBRARY for research articles published up to March, 2023 with no language restrictions. NRT is relatively unlikely to help smokers who are not motivated to quit or do not experience or expect to experience nicotine withdrawal symptoms. The Nicotine Replacement Therapy helps by timely delivering pure nicotine, and therefore poses less risk and reduces cravings. Several nicotine medications are available in different forms, doses and flavours.

Keywords: Smoking cessations aids, NRT, nicotine substitutes, quit aids, nicotine cessation products

Introduction

In 1980, a pivotal moment occurred in the field of mental health with the inclusion of "nicotine dependence" in the third edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM). Subsequently, in 1988, the US Surgeon General released a landmark report titled "The health consequences of smoking: nicotine and addiction," officially characterizing tobacco smoking as an addictive behavior. The evolution of this concept continued with the American Psychiatric Association establishing current diagnostic criteria for nicotine dependence in the DSM fourth edition-text revised (DSM-IV-TR), and the World Health Organization contributing to this framework in the International Classification of Diseases, 10th revision (ICD-10). These standardized criteria have become essential tools for the identification and classification of nicotine

dependence, reflecting the ongoing recognition of smoking as a significant public health concern with distinct mental health implications¹.

India is the world's second largest producer of tobacco. The tobacco industry in India includes the production, distribution and consumption of (i) leaf tobacco, (ii) smoking products such as cigarettes and beedis and (iii) various chewing tobacco products. There are public health concerns about the effects of smoking and consumer-led lobbies asking for more controls on cigarette sales, smoking and advertising. In spite of its proven adverse implications for public health, the industry continues to be supported in many quarters on the grounds of its contribution to employment and national production. The organized sector of the industry, dominated by multinational corporations, is at the forefront of canvassing support for the sector.²

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Evidence indicates that people smoke primarily to experience the psychopharmacological properties of nicotine and that the majority of smokers eventually become dependent upon nicotine (Balfour, 1984; Stolerman, 1991)³

Tobacco dependence is defined as, “Cluster of behavioural, cognitive and physiological phenomena that develop after repeated tobacco use and that typically include a strong desire to use tobacco, difficulties in controlling its use, persistence in tobacco use despite harmful consequences, a higher priority given to tobacco use than other activities and obligations, increased tolerance and sometimes a physical withdrawal state.”⁴ Both smoked and smokeless forms of tobacco contain nicotine, a highly addictive chemical, making it difficult for habituated tobacco users to quit.⁴

Physical And Psychological Effects of Nicotine

In humans, nicotine from tobacco smoking produces a mild pleasurable rush, euphoria, increased arousal, decreased fatigue and relaxation. Absorption of cigarette smoke from the lung is rapid and complete, producing with each inhalation a high concentration arterial bolus of nicotine that reaches the brain within 10-16 seconds, faster than by intravenous injection. Nicotine has a distributional half life of 15-20 minutes and a terminal half life in blood of two hours. Smokers therefore experience a pattern of repetitive and transient high blood nicotine concentration from each cigarette, with regular hourly cigarettes needed to maintain raised concentration, and overnight blood levels dropping to close to those of non-smokers.

Resumption of smoking often occurs upon exposure to people, places, objects or other environmental or social stimuli that individuals have learned to associate with the positive rewarding effects of nicotine. These associations can trigger intense cravings that lead to relapse in abstinent smokers.⁵ The pharmacological responses that contribute to both the reinforcing effects of nicotine during smoking and the craving symptoms upon smoking cessation are mediated through various nAcetyl Choline Receptors subtypes located in different brain areas. The nicotine-induced release of dopamine in the mesolimbic reward pathway initiates physiological response that contributes to the reinforcing effects of nicotine. It is believed that the rapidly recurring and transitory increases in mesolimbic dopamine levels following repeated exposure to, and withdrawal from, nicotine transmit salient reward and aversive signals to higher cortical centres, facilitating the

learning and associations that lead to physical dependence, characterized by both somatic and psychoactive symptoms. Tobacco products consist largely of the inorganic compounds nitrogen (N₂), oxygen (O₂), carbon monoxide (CO), carbon dioxide (CO₂), hydrogen cyanide (HCN), nitric acid, hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) and a large number of volatile organic compounds such as acetaldehyde, acrolein, ammonia, methanol, certain nitrosamines and carbonyls.⁶ Smoking causes atherosclerosis, Cancer of (Lung, Larynx, Oral, Oesophagus, Stomach, Liver, Pancreas, Colon, Kidney and Ureter, Cervix, Bladder and Acute myeloid leukaemia.) and chronic diseases like Blindness, cataract, Age related macular degeneration, Periodontitis, Osteoporosis, Reproductive disturbances, Erectile dysfunction, Diabetes mellitus, Altered immune function. Passive smoking is the exposure to second-hand smoke (SHS) or third-hand smoke by inhalation of ambient air containing various toxic substances resulting from the combustion products of tobacco after birth, or exposure to maternal blood contaminated with the combustion products of tobacco smoking in utero.⁷

Who should receive NRT?

Nicotine replacement therapy, preferably in conjunction with behavioural support, should generally be offered to any regular cigarette smoker prepared to make a quit attempt.⁸ NRT is relatively unlikely to help smokers who are not motivated to quit or do not experience or expect to experience nicotine withdrawal symptoms. Any healthcare professionals can assess these characteristics in the following ways:

- 1. Motivation to quit:** smokers should be asked whether they would like to stop smoking. Those willing to stop within the next 30 days should set a quit date and their dependence should be assessed.⁸
- 2. Dependence:** smokers should be asked whether they have tried to quit smoking before, whether they experienced symptoms of nicotine withdrawal, and whether they anticipate these symptoms in a future quit attempt. The main mode of action of NRT is thought to be the stimulation of nicotinic receptors in the ventral tegmental area of the brain and the consequent release of dopamine in the nucleus accumbens. This and other peripheral actions of nicotine lead to a reduction in nicotine withdrawal symptoms in regular smokers who abstain from smoking. NRT may also provide a coping mechanism, making cigarettes less rewarding to smoke.⁸

Smoking cessation with NRT is approximately eight times more cost-effective per saved quality-adjusted life year compared with 300 medical treatments for diseases such as hypertension, hypercholesterolemia and COPD . There are some basic principles related to successful smoking cessation that are important for the therapist to consider and this seems to be especially important for NRT use: smokers must stop smoking completely at a target quit day (even 1 or 2 cigarettes per day during the first 1 or 2 weeks of cessation are usually followed by relapse). Below are some other important statements about NRT:

- 1) The use of NRT lessens withdrawal symptoms and improves cessation outcome.
- 2) For patients with respiratory disorders, aggressive use of NRT is recommended.
- 3) Follow-up should be arranged to prevent relapse (which is highest during the first 3–6 weeks, then gradually declines, similarly to other addictions).
- 4) Smoking reduction might be a gateway to smoking cessation in smokers low in motivation to quit.
- 5) If the patient relapses, he or she should be encouraged to make another attempt to quit later on and then receive re-treatment .⁹

Types NRT	Dosage	How to use them	Warning	Adverse effects	Availability	Brand names
Transdermal patches	5,10,15mg doses worn over 16 h, 7,14,21 mg doses worn over 24 h.	One daily on clean, unbroken skin; remove before bed(16h patch)or next morning (24h); new patch, fresh site Give a small and steady amount of nicotine.	Places on the skin, give a small and steady amount of nicotine.	Local skin reaction Insomnia	US FDA (OTC) MHRA (OTC)	Habitrol Nicoderm CQ Nicotrol
Chewing gum	2 mg and 4 mg doses	Chew to release nicotine chew until you get a tingling feeling, then place between cheek and gums	TMJ diseases Caution with dentures Do not eat or drink 15 min before or during use	Mouth soreness Hiccups Dyspepsia Jaw ache	US FDA (OTC) MHRA (OTC)	Nicorette Nulife Nicotex
Sublingual Tablets	2 mg dose	Rest under tongue until dissolved	Nicotine dependence Insomnia	Mouth soreness	MHRA (Rx) regulatory	
Lozenge	1mg,2 mg, 4 mg doses	Place in mouth like hard candy Release nicotine as it slowly dissolves in the mouth Allow to dissolve in mouth (about 20-30 min), moving from side to side from time to time. Try not to swallow excessively. Do not chew or swallow whole	Do not eat or drink 15 min before or during use one lozenge at a time limit 20 in 24 h	Nausea/heartburn	US FDA (OTC) MHRA (OTC)	Commit
Nasal Spray	0.5 mg dose /spray	Pump bottle containing nicotine Put into nose and spray Take swallow puffs approximately every 2s or alternatively take four puffs every minute Continue for up to 30 mins.	Notfor patients with asthma may cause dependence	Nasal irritation	US FDA (Rx) MHRA	Nicotrol Inhaler
Electronic cigarettes		E-cigarettes vapor is drawn very slowly in to mouth, then held there for a second or two. Then , it can be inhaled if desired The vapours is then expelled through the mouth or nose.	May cause dependence	Mouth & airway irritation Chest pain Palpitation	Until now, it is not approved by any agency	Vaporfi V2cigs, JUUL, Sout h beach smoke, HALO cigs

Non	Nicotine	Replacement	Therapy			
Bupropion	150 mg OD for 3 days followed by 150 mg BD for 7 to 12 weeks			Agitation, restlessness, git upset, headache, anorexia		
Varenicline	initially 0.5 mg for the first three days, increase to 0.5 mg twice daily for the next four days			bad dreams, suicidal ideations, allergic rx, insomnia		

Table:1 Types of nicotine replacement therapy and formulations¹⁰

Transdermal Patches

Transdermal patches are a common form of NRT those are applied to the skin and deliver nicotine through the skin at a relatively steady rate.¹⁰ Transdermal drug delivery has been the leading edge over injectables and oral routes by enhancing patient compliance and bypassing first pass metabolism respectively.¹¹ Patches are available in a range of dosages, which permits higher dependent smokers to use the strongest patches and lower-dependent smokers to use a lower. The range of dosages allows users to gradually decrease their nicotine intake over a period of several weeks or longer to enable a gradual adjustment of their bodies to lower nicotine levels and ultimately to a nicotine-free state.¹² Nicotine patch is simple to use. The patient can place the nicotine patch over the skin once in the morning, rather than using throughout the day. There is a slow release of nicotine when compared to other acute NRT products. Plasma concentration of nicotine gets elevated during the day with patch use than with acute NRT use. Dose can range from 5 to 22 mg of nicotine over a 24 h period, resulting in plasma levels similar levels seen in heavy smokers.¹³ Side effects include mouth and skin irritations, increased heart rates and higher blood pressure readings and sleep disturbances.¹⁰ To avoid skin irritation, the site of application of patch has to be changed daily. Insomnia has also been reported with 24 h patches.¹⁴ Transdermal nicotine has been shown to be of benefit as an aid to smoking cessation and is a prominent feature of the Clinical Practice Guideline for smoking cessation of the Agency for Health Care Policy and Research.

Components of a Transdermal Patch

Transdermal patch may consist of the following components:

1. Liner - It protects the patch during storage. It is removed prior to use.

- 2. Drug** - Drug solution is in direct contact with release liner.
- 3. Adhesive**- It serve to adhere the components of the patch together along with adhering the patch to the skin.
- 4. Membrane**- It is used to control the release of the drug from the reservoir and multi-layer patches.
- 5. Backing**- It protects the patch from the outer environment.

Types of Transdermal Patches

There are mainly five types of transdermal patches listed below:

1. Single-layer Drug-in-Adhesive:

The adhesive layer of this system is provided with the drug surrounded by a temporary liner and backing. This layer is responsible for adhering the various layer together, along with the release of a drug.

2. Multi-layer Drug-in-Adhesive:

The multilayer drug-in adhesive patch has a close similarity with single-layer system in that ,both adhesive layers are responsible for therelease of the drug. The multi-layer system has additional layer of drug-in-adhesive, that is usually separated by a membrane (in many cases). This type of patch also has a permanent backing associated with the temporary liner layer.

3. Drug Reservoir-In-Adhesive:

Unlike the Single-layer and Multi-layer Drug-in adhesive systems the drug reservoir–in-adhesive system has a separate drug layer. The drug layer is in the form of drug solution or suspension that has been separated by the adhesive layer. Backing layer is also provided with this patch., Zero order kinetics is followed in this type of system.

4. Drug Matrix-In-Adhesive:

In this type of transdermal patch, the Matrix system is associated with a drug layer which is in the form of semisolid matrix containing a drug solution or suspension. The adhesive layer in this patch surrounds the drug layer partially overlaying it.

5. Vapour Patch:

The vapour patch performs basically two functions, first one is to adhere the various layers and the second one is to release vapour. The vapour patches have been introduced recently in the market and essential oils are released from them for up to 6 hours, due to this property, the vapour patches are used in cases of decongestion mainly.¹¹

Transdermal patches are used:

1. When side effects are intolerable (including constipation) in the patient and who is finding difficulty in oral medication (dysphagia).
2. Where the pain control might be improved by suitable administration. This might be useful in patients suffering from cognitive impairment or those who for other reasons are not able to self-medicate with their analgesia..

Unfavourable condition for transdermal patch used:

1. When there is acute pain condition.
2. Where rapid dose titration is required.
3. Where requirement of dose is equal to or less than 30 mg/24 hrs.

Care taken while using transdermal patch:

1. The part of the skin should be properly cleaned where the patch is to be applied.
2. The system of patch should be free from cut because the drug delivery system is destroyed by the cut in the patch.
3. Before applying a new patch it should be made clear enough that the old patch is removed from the site.
4. Patch should be applied and removed carefully because the persons handling the patch can absorb the drug from the patch.
5. There should be accurate application of patch to the site of administration.

Recent advancements in transdermal drug delivery:

1. Carbon Nanotube Membranes:

Recently, a novel skin patch tool for the delivery of the nicotine was developed by Dr. Hinds and his colleagues

which were basically based on the technology in which Carbon nanotubes (CNT) of approximate diameter 2- 6.5 nm are aligned in such a way to form an active layer in a solid film of polymer. During the process both ends Carbon nanotubes are adapted in such a way that by mere applying and removing the electric current the cross-linking can be opened or closed.²⁷ In his research, Dr. Hinds had shown that when the carbon nanotubes are in the patch are arranged in the open condition, molecules having small molecular weight can be pumped through the patch atleast five times quicker. So, the CNT patch can also be considered as system for the delivery of the drug or nicotine that can be controlled by the physician or the user in order to obtain the comparable plasma levels of nicotine as associated with the cigarette smoking and then allowed to return to the normal levels slowly by closing the CNT ends by removing the electric current. Besides the controlled transdermal delivery of the Nicotine, the CNT patch can also be used for other skin absorbable drugs.

2) Microneedle-Based Transdermal Drug Delivery System:

Transdermal drug delivery involves the passing of pharmaceutical compound across the dermis of the skin for subsequent systemic distribution. The most important advantage of this approach is that the drug is released into the body undistorted without passing the body's various defence systems. The transdermal route does not suffer from drug degradation in the gastrointestinal tract and decreased potency through first-pass metabolism (i.e. in the liver). Further, the oral-specific side effects, such as liver damages, are avoided.

Nicotine Chewing Gums

Nicotine polacrilex (nicotine gum) was the first commercially available NRT product. The chewing gum is one of the new methods of oral transmucosal drug delivery and is a useful tool for systemic drug delivery.¹⁵ Nicotine gum is chewed intermittently and retained in the mouth for approximately 30 min for the release of nicotine.¹¹ It is available in both 2 mg and 4 mg dosages. More success rate of withdrawal was achieved with 4 mg chewable gum. The number of doses per day is reduced gradually after a few weeks or months until it is no longer required. Gum users should only chew a piece of gum five to ten times until they can taste the nicotine, then let the gum rest in the cheek for a few minutes and then chew again to expose a new surface of the gum.⁹ The gum can be chewed

for about 20–30 min. About 0.8–1.2 mg of nicotine is absorbed from a piece of 2-mg nicotine gum, and 1.2–1.5 mg of nicotine from a 4-mg piece. Using nicotine gum throughout the day, blood levels of one third (for 2-mg gum) and two thirds (for 4-mg gum) of the nicotine obtained through smoking of approximately a mean of 20 cigarettes/day are achieved, remembering that smokers often self-titrate the dose to achieve the desired nicotine level.

Nicotine Lozenges

The 2-mg sublingual tablet should be placed under the tongue where it will disintegrate within 20 min while the 1- or 2-mg lozenge should be sucked at until a strong taste appears and then rest in the cheek for a few minutes, and then repeat the cycle for 15–20 min.⁹ The nicotine released from the 'tablets' will be absorbed through the oral mucous membrane and the dose delivered is comparable with the 2-mg nicotine chewing gum. The tablets/lozenges should be used for 3 months, but duration of treatment should be individualised for up to 1 year or longer. One tablet per hour is the recommended dosage up to 20/day, with a maximum dose of up to 40 'tablets'/day in highly dependent smokers.⁹ The lozenges provides an alternative to the gum for persons who need intermittent and controllable nicotine dosing but who do not find gum chewing acceptable. The amount of nicotine absorbed per lozenges appears to be somewhat higher than that delivered by gum.¹⁰ It is used to relieve and prevent withdrawal symptoms and reduce the cravings you get when you try to stop smoking or when cutting down the number of cigarettes person smokes and at the places where person do not want to smoke to avoid harm to others specially in front of children or family, smoke free areas like aeroplanes, pubs or work places. It may also help increase your motivation to quit when making a quit attempt behavioural support programme.

Nicotine Sublingual Tablets

Many smokers are unable to use gum as a cessation aid due to fillings, bridgework and dyspepsia or they reject it for aesthetic reasons. The nicotine sublingual tablet is a new alternative to the nicotine polacrilex chewing gum that does not necessitate chewing.¹⁶ The tablet contains 2 mg of nicotine as a nicotine-b-cyclodextrin complex.¹⁷ It is held under the tongue where the nicotine in the tablet is absorbed sublingually. The levels of nicotine obtained by use of the 2 mg lozenge and 2 mg sublingual tablet are similar. It is

recommended that smokers use the product for at least 12 weeks. After 12 weeks, the number of tablets used should be gradually tapered.¹⁸ Thus the nicotine 2-mg sublingual tablet was effective as a smoking cessation aid.¹⁹ Microtabs are fast acting, like nicotine gum, but the microtabs are more discreet than the gums and simpler to use. Microtabs rapidly relieve irritability, food cravings, mood swings, concentration difficulties, the urge to smoke and other inconveniences that may occur in smoking cessation.

Nicotine Oral Spray

There is some evidence that NRT formulations that act faster in relieving cravings for cigarettes are overall more effective at relieving withdrawal discomfort. Nicotine nasal spray has more immediate effects but it initially causes unpleasant local irritation. Delivering nicotine via a mouth spray is one promising approach to a faster and more palatable form of nicotine delivery. Compared with chewing gum, lozenge or sublingual tablet, mouth spray delivers nicotine in solution quickly on a large surface area of the buccal mucosa. A nicotine mouth spray provided a safe and effective smoking cessation option for smokers motivated to quit, even in naturalistic settings and without behavioural support, according to findings recently published in *Nicotine & Tobacco Research*.²⁰ It consists of a mouthpiece and a plastic cartridge containing nicotine. Majority of nicotine from the inhaler is delivered into the oral cavity (36%), oesophagus and stomach (36%), and very little to the lung (4%). The rate of absorption is similar to that of nicotine gum. Each inhaler cartridge contains 10 mg nicotine, of which up to 4 mg can be delivered and 2 mg can be absorbed following frequent "puffing."¹⁰ A new nicotine mouth spray (NMS), which delivers 1 mg nicotine per spray, has been developed to enable more rapid nicotine absorption than from existing oral NRT. formats.²¹ A craving relief study demonstrated that 2 doses of NMS 1 mg reduced craving significantly faster than either nicotine lozenge 2 mg or 4 mg.²²

Nicotine Inhalers

An inhaler consists of a mouthpiece and a plastic tube with a porous plug impregnated with nicotine, which releases nicotine vapour when air is drawn through the plug.⁹ Most of the nicotine is absorbed through the mouth and throat. Each inhaler contains 10 mg of nicotine. In clinical use, each inhaler releases approximately 2–3 mg of nicotine, and the number of inhalers used daily averages 5–6. Thus, nicotine levels are comparable to those found

during use of the 2-mg nicotine gum are attainable (i.e. relatively low concentrations). The inhaler may replace some of the habit patterns associated with smoking (i.e. oral and handling reinforcement), along with providing nicotine replacement. At least four inhalers should be used per day, the optimal number being 4–10 per day, and the duration of use 3 months, with another 3–9 months of use and down titration if needed.

E-Cigarettes

Electronic cigarettes are a class of battery-powered devices designed as an alternative to tobacco smoking, that were invented by the Chinese engineer HonLick in the early 2000s.²³ Electronic cigarettes (ECs) a new class of electronic nicotine delivery system, introduced in 2004.²⁴ Each device contains an electronic vaporization system, rechargeable batteries, electronic controls and cartridges of the liquid that is vaporized. The liquid usually contains glycerol, propylene glycol, water, nicotine and a variety of flavouring additives. When activated by the user, the heating element atomizes the liquid, resulting in aerosolized nicotine vapor and a visible plume, this vapor is inhaled into the lungs called 'vaping', where nicotine is absorbed. It was hypothesised that e-cigarettes may reduce cravings more effectively than NRT, have of better adherence rates and delivery of clinically significant levels of nicotine into the blood.

High Dose Nicotine Patches

The conventional patches of 22-mg patch can only replace approximately half of the baseline serum nicotine and cotinine levels in smokers. Therefore, higher transdermal nicotine doses of ≥ 42 mg were evaluated. In terms of efficacy, a numerically higher abstinence rate was achieved with high-dose transdermal NRT.

Rapid Release Gum

A rapid-release gum has been formulated to provide biphasic nicotine delivery, starting with accelerated delivery to promote rapid craving relief and then levelling off to avoid overdosing.²⁵ The rapid-release gum achieved faster and more complete craving relief, differentiating itself from current nicotine gum.

Combining Two Different Nicotine Replacement Products

A strategy for further improving the efficacy of NRT is to combine one medication that allows for passive nicotine delivery (e.g. transdermal patch) with another medication that permits ad libitum nicotine delivery (e.g. gum, nasal

spray, inhaler).¹² The rationale for combining NRT medications is that smokers may need both a slow delivery system to achieve a constant concentration of nicotine to relieve cravings and tobacco-withdrawal symptoms, as well as a faster acting preparation that can be administered on demand for immediate relief of break through cravings and withdrawal symptoms. The patch provides nicotine in a steady-state and passive form while gum can be manipulated to accommodate the users' needs. product alone. Combining the nicotine patch with an oral form of NRT has been shown to increase quit rates by 34–54% compared to using the patch alone.

The Future Nicotine Preloading

The use of nicotine replacement therapy before quitting smoking is called nicotine preloading.²⁴ This approach involves using NRT for a several weeks prior to quitting; it is also known as pre-cessation or pre-quitting NRT. The most plausible mechanisms include habituation with use of NRT in the lead-up to quitting, attenuation of desire to smoke due to nicotine receptor saturation and it reduces satisfaction from smoking by which it undermines the learned association between smoking and reward.

True Pulmonary Inhaler

A true pulmonary inhaler, unlike the currently available nicotine inhaler, would deliver nicotine to the lung in a manner more comparable to cigarette smoking.¹² This would be predicted to deliver a dose of nicotine sufficient to reduce background cravings and withdrawal symptoms, and would allow for rapid relief of acute cravings and morning craving. Because the delivery of nicotine directly to the lung would effectively mimic the effects of cigarette smoking on a physiologic level, the smoker could eliminate the need for tobacco, and subsequently taper the nicotine level over time to alleviate dependence upon altogether.

Long-Term Nicotine Replacement Therapy

Long-term NRT can arbitrary be defined as NRT use after 12 months. The prevalence is not very precise from data in the literature and has been reported as low as 1–2% up to 25%. On average, ~5–10% of abstainers still use NRT after 12 months.²² It is not a new nicotine dependence on NRT but rather than ex-smokers have not been able to break the addiction to nicotine already existing. It is the acute formulations of NRT that are used in the long term, i.e. mainly gums, sublingual tablets and inhalers, while nobody misuses the patch

Nicotine Vaccines

Nicotine vaccines represent a new approach to the treatment of nicotine dependence and are currently under investigation.¹² Because nicotine is a small molecule and an incomplete antigen, it is linked to a carrier protein order to stimulate the necessary immune response. The nicotine conjugate vaccine acts by mobilising drug specific antibodies, which bind the nicotine molecules in the blood and prevent the drug from distributing to the brain, thereby

reducing its behavioural effects. The nicotine addict will not experience any satisfaction from smoking and a first time user cannot become addicted.²⁴

A number of organizations have developed vaccines for smoking cessation, with Nic VAX developed by Nabi Biopharmaceuticals being perhaps the best known. Phase I and II studies have evaluated three different vaccines, Nic VAX, Nic Qb and TA-NIC. Dosing has been 2–6 injections at intervals of 2–4 weeks and a later booster dose.⁹

Vaccine	Sponsor	Clinical trial Phase	Results
NicVax (Bacterial exoprotein Conjugate vaccine)	Nabi Biopharmaceuticals	III	The preliminary results of the trials showed that the primary end point of 16 weeks abstinence measured at 12 months was not met; there was no statistically difference between the NicVAXW and placebo group (56)
NIC002 (Nicotine Qbeta or CYT002- NicQb)	Novartis	II	Interim analysis showed that the primary endpoint (continuous abstinence from smoking from weeks 8–12 after start of treatment) was not achieved, possibly because NIC002 failed to induce sufficiently high antibody titers. (57,58)
TA-NIC (a recombinant cholera toxin conjugate vaccine)	Celtic Pharma	II	Not declared
SEL-068 (Synthetically engineered nanoparticle)	Selecta Biosciences	I	Not declared

Table :2 Novel Biological or Vaccine Agents in Clinical Testing for Smoking Cessation¹²

Varenicline

Varenicline not only acts as a partial agonist to attenuate withdrawal symptoms during smoking cessation, but also as an agent to block nicotine binding.²⁵ In combination with counselling, varenicline increases long-term quit rates two and threefold compared to no-drug treatment. In COPD patients and patients with cardiovascular disorders, varenicline has shown to be particularly effective. It is a good idea to taper the number of cigarettes during the 1st week of therapy, waiting for the concentration of varenicline to build up in the brain, and then, after 1–2 weeks, set a target quit day where the smoker stops completely cigarette smoking. Nausea, abnormal dreams, upper-respiratory-tract infection and insomnia, suicidal behaviour and myocardial infarction are the most common adverse effects, and present depression is a relative contraindication with the use of varenicline.

Bupropion SR Bupropion SR (tablets) is an older antidepressant, drug but its effect on smoking cessation is not related to its anti depressive effect. More recently, sustained-release bupropion, 150 mg. taken twice daily, has been evaluated and found to be either equivalent or slightly superior in efficacy to NRT.

Secondary Drug For Smoking Cessation Cytisine

Cytisine is a natural drug extracted from the seeds of the plant Golden Rain and is a nicotine receptor partial agonists as the synthetic drug varenicline.²² Gastro intestinal effects is higher with the use of cytisine.

Nortriptyline Nortriptyline, a tricyclic antidepressant, is the only other antidepressant (i.e. bupropion SR) that has demonstrated evidence of efficacy for smoking cessation.⁹ The dose of nortriptyline for smoking cessation is 75–150 mg/day..

Clonidine Clonidine, an imidazoline drug previously used in the management of hypertension, has limited efficacy as smoking cessation therapy. It has been recommended as second-line therapy in US smoking cessation guidelines.⁹

Side Effects of NRT

The side effects of NRT may be discomforting for the patient but not life threatening.²³ Generally, the side effects are mild and are present in the local area only, i.e. the mouth for oral types and the skin for patches.

The most commonly seen side effects of NRT includes heart palpitations/chest pains, nausea/vomiting (oral products only), indigestion or gastrointestinal complaints (higher risk with oral products), insomnia (patch), skin irritation (patch), mouth and throat soreness (oral products), mouth ulcers (oral products), and coughing (oral products). Significant medical problems due to NRT are extremely rare. To calculate relative risk, the side effects of NRT should be compared with the side effects of smoking. Cigarettes contain 69 identified cancer-causing substances, which are absent in medicinal Nicotine. Thus, the NRT is much safer than smoking.

Conclusion

Nicotine addiction is the major cause of failure of smoking cessation. The Nicotine Replacement Therapy helps by timely delivering pure nicotine, and therefore poses less risk and reduces cravings. Several nicotine medications are available in different forms, doses and flavours. The choice of NRT product should normally be guided by the patient's preference. Evidence suggests that, NRT increases the chances of successfully stopping smoking and long-term abstinence. The dentist and the office team has the responsibility to encourage patients to quit tobacco use by pointing out the damage caused by tobacco to oral tissues and highlighting the general health benefits of quitting. Besides modifying risk behaviour, prescribing approved pharmaceutical agents is known to increase the quit rates. For all patients' sake, the dental office must continue to work towards universal adoption of tobacco cessation intervention. To improve the efficacy of NRT recently research is more focusing on rapid delivery techniques and immunological techniques. These new modalities require more quality research to bring it from bench to bedside. Beholding the potential capacity of NRT, it's essential for health professionals to become familiar with all forms of NRT to be able to address the questions and needs of tobacco users who appear to be increasingly interested in tobacco cessation.

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